

Insider Threat Detection Using Machine Learning Techniques

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Abstract—cyber security is important nowadays and mostly the attack is from insiders is called insider threat. The insider threat has mainly happened in the organization and the insiders that are the workers in the organization may be the cause of creating the threat. The people can have access to the organization they are creating a threat against the organization for their benefit. The insider threat attacks mainly happen through emails. This study mainly focuses on whether an email is spam or ham using a machine learning model by analyzing a data set containing spam and ham mails.

Keywords—Insider threat, machine learning, logistic regression, feature extraction.

I. INTRODUCTION

Cyber security threats are important in our latest technology. Identifying and handling the threats is very difficult, especially handling insider threats. Insider threats may come from the users who have access to the organization.

Insiders are aware of organizational security procedures and can quickly uncover loopholes, as well as rules enacted by the organization. The insiders can send malicious mail to their colleagues in the same organization. The study is aimed to check the mail content whether it is malicious mail or not, by using machine learning techniques. Creating a machine learning model by use of logistic regression and finding the accuracy

The method for detecting insider threat

- Data collection and data pre-processing
- Creating machine learning model by logistic regression method
- Compares the accuracy of the training data and the test data

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

[1] A research paper is mainly aimed to find the insider threat using machine learning techniques by analyzing a malicious dataset (TWOS). The machine learning algorithms like AdaBoost, naïve Bayes, linear regression, logistic regression, KNN, and SVM are and finally AdaBoost has performed 98.3 accuracies for identifying malicious mail.

[2] The article is aimed to present a solution for identifying spam mail content by using machine learning models like Naïve Bayes, SVM, Random Forest, Decision Tree, and Multi-Layer Perceptron also using feature extraction and pre-processing techniques on different seven data sets. On the Spam Assassin dataset, the greatest accuracy was achieved using GA optimization on randomized data distribution for an 80:20 train and test split set.

[3] The paper is discussing identifying spam mail with techniques of machine learning the mainly used algorithms are Naïve Bayes, support vector machine-nearest neighbor, random forest, bagging, boosting, and neural networks. As the result, the naïve Bayes is giving the best outcome.

[4] The study is based on the naïve Bayes algorithm produces a better result with accuracy is 91%.

[5] This study is a combination of logistic regression and a Decision tree for the detection of spam mail. Logistic regression is used for reducing the noise of data. Spam mail data set is used in the study. The use of logistic regression with the FN threshold is reducing the noise of data and results in the decision tree increasing its performance. The study result is yield excellent accuracy is 91.67.

III. METHODOLOGY

The study is aimed to detect whether a mail is spam or ham, the spam mail dataset is used for developing the machine learning model. The dataset is mainly classified into a training dataset and a test dataset. This resulting model uses to predict spam mails.

Requirements:

- CSV file
- PyCharm

The logistic regression method is used for creating the machine learning model. Logistic regression is all about predicting the value or probability when a binary event occurred.

Structure of the process

Figure 1: Insider threat detection using ml techniques

Methodology

Steps required for the process

- Data collection
- Data pre-processing
- Feature extraction
- Training the model
- Evaluating the trainingmodel
- Building the predictivemodel

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

Main steps to building the predictive model

```

import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import tkinter as tk
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.feature_extraction.text import TfidfVectorizer
from sklearn.linear_model import LogisticRegression
from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score
    
```

Figure 1: import the necessary package

```

print(raw_mail_data)
mail_data = raw_mail_data.where((pd.notnull(raw_mail_data))._)
mail_data.head()
mail_data.shape
mail_data.loc[mail_data['Category'] == 'spam', 'Category'] = 0
mail_data.loc[mail_data['Category'] == 'ham', 'Category'] = 1
X = mail_data['Message']

Y = mail_data['Category']
print(X)
print(Y)
    
```

Figure 2: Data collection and pre-processing

```

X_train, X_test, Y_train, Y_test = train_test_split(X, Y, test_size=0.2, random_state=3)
print(X.shape)
print(X_train.shape)
print(X_test.shape)
    
```

Figure 3: Splitting the data set

```

feature_extraction = TfidfVectorizer(min_df=1, stop_words='english', lowercase='True')

X_train_features = feature_extraction.fit_transform(X_train)
X_test_features = feature_extraction.transform(X_test)

# convert Y_train and Y_test values as integers

Y_train = Y_train.astype('int')
Y_test = Y_test.astype('int')
print(X_train)
print(X_train_features)
    
```

Figure 4: Feature extraction

```

model = LogisticRegression()
model.fit(X_train_features, Y_train)
prediction_on_training_data = model.predict(X_train_features)
accuracy_on_training_data = accuracy_score(Y_train, prediction_on_training_data)
print('Accuracy on training data : ', accuracy_on_training_data)
    
```

Figure 5: Training the model and accuracy

The accuracy obtained is 96.70

```
input_mail = [x1]

# convert text to feature vectors
input_data_features = feature_extraction.transform(input_mail)

# making prediction
prediction = model.predict(input_data_features)
print(prediction)

if (prediction[0]==1):
    label3 = tk.Label(root, text='Ham', font=('helvetica', 10))
    canvas1.create_window(200, 210, window=label3)

else:
    label3 = tk.Label(root, text='spam', font=('helvetica', 10))
    canvas1.create_window(200, 210, window=label3)

button1 = tk.Button(text='check mail content', command=getSquareRoot, bg='brown', fg='white',
                    font=('helvetica', 9, 'bold'))
canvas1.create_window(200, 180, window=button1)

root.mainloop()
```

Figure 6: Building a predictive model

V. RESULT

The result shows that the whether the mail content is spam or ham

```
(4456, 6249) 0.17573831794959716
(4456, 6307) 0.2752760476857975
(4456, 334) 0.2220077711654938
(4456, 5778) 0.16243064490100795
(4456, 2870) 0.31523196273113385
Accuracy on training data : 0.9670181736594121
[1]
```

Figure 7:Accuracy

Figure 8: check whether the email is spam or not

Figure 8: check whether an email is spam or not

Figure 9: Percentage of spam and ham in the given dataset

VI. CONCLUSION

This study provides a method for detecting the insider threat by using a machine learning technique with analysing a spam data set it will predict whether a mail is a spam or not. This paper uses the best machine technique for detecting spam mail and also uses the TF- IDF vectorizer technique. The experiment provides better accuracy.

VII.REFERENCES

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